

Bromide-catalysed Oxidation of Arsenic(III) by Manganese(III) in Acid Medium

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Manuscript received 14 January 1994, accepted 17 February 1994

Halide-catalysed Mn^{III} oxidation of As^{III} goes through complex such as $AsBr^{2+}$ and through As^{4+} . No acid or product effect is found. A mechanism is proposed and derived rate law is verified. Some constants involved in the mechanism are derived. Rates calculated using the derived constants are in reasonable agreement with the experimental rates.

The importance of bridging anions in facilitating electron transfer in inorganic reactions is well-known. A chloride ion bridge accelerated mechanism has been found in many exchange reactions¹⁻³. In case of redox reactions where halide catalysis is appreciable, it is desirable to know whether the catalysis occurs through complexation or is simply an anion effect. In case of oxidation³, of As^{III} , Sb^{III} and Tl , influence of halides is pronounced. Thus in the oxidation of Tl^I by Mn^{III} in presence of chloride⁴, not only Tl^{II} but also species like $MnCl_2^{2+}$ and Cl_2^- intervene.

It is well known that As^{III} forms several stable halide complexes. The bromide catalysis of Mn^{III} - As^{III} reaction has not been studied. The rate acceleration of this reaction in presence of halide may be due to the formation of As^{III} -halide complex, Mn^{III} -halide complex or be due to general anion effect. In view of such possibilities a study of the Mn^{III} - As^{III} reaction catalysed by bromide in aqueous sulphuric acid was undertaken and the results are furnished here.

Results and Discussion

The order in oxidant, reductant and catalyst was determined from log-log plots of initial rates against concentrations. Under the conditions of reaction ($5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$, and $I = 5.6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), the reaction between Mn^{III} ($5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and bromide ($5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was very slow, the initial

rate being $5.0 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. At a fixed As^{III} concentration of 1.0×10^{-2} , $5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and $I = 5.6 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at 25° , the order in Mn^{III} concentration in the range 1.3×10^{-3} – $1.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ was found to be unity (Table 1). Under similar conditions of acidity, ionic strength and temperature, at $[Mn^{III}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $[As^{III}] = 4.0 \times 10^{-3}$ – $4.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the order in $[As^{III}]$ was ~ 0.6 (Table 1). The effect of catalyst was studied in the range of 1.0×10^{-5} – $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and the order in catalyst is found to be 0.5 (Table 1). The effect of acid concentration of the reaction rate was studied in the range of 3.0 – 5.0 mol dm^{-3} . Higher concentration is preferred, since at low acid concentrations the oxidant is unstable. The effect of acid was studied at constant ionic strength (5.6 mol dm^{-3}). There is no significant effect of acid on the initial rate of reaction. The effects of products, As^V and Mn^{II} were studied in the range 1.0×10^{-3} – 1.0×10^{-2} and 1.0×10^{-3} – $4.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ respectively, keeping all other conditions constant. The As^V and Mn^{II} did not alter the reaction rate significantly.

Test for polymerisation : Under the reaction conditions (Table 1) the reaction was allowed to take place in presence of 0.01 mol dm^{-3} acrylamide. After the completion of the reaction, the solution was diluted with methanol and this resulted in the formation of a precipitate.

Effect of temperature : The effect of temperature

was studied at 25, 30, 35 and 40°. Since the evaluation of rate constants of different steps in the reaction scheme was not possible, the activation parameters were not calculated.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [As^{III}], [Mn^{III}], [Br⁻] IN BROMIDE CATALYSED OXIDATION OF As^{III} BY Mn^{III}

Temp = 25°, [H₂SO₄] = 5.0, I = 5.60 mol dm⁻³

[As ^{III}] × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	[Mn ^{III}] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[Br ⁻] × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³	Initial rates × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	
			Expt	Calcd *
0.4	5.00	5.00	3.0	3.0
0.6	5.00	5.00	3.8	4.0
1.0	5.00	5.00	5.3	5.9
2.0	5.00	5.00	7.9	8.6
3.0	5.00	5.00	9.9	10.1
4.0	5.00	5.00	11.1	11.1
1.00	1.3	5.00	1.0	1.2
1.00	2.0	5.00	2.0	2.3
1.00	3.0	5.00	3.5	3.6
1.00	5.0	5.00	5.3	5.9
1.00	6.5	5.00	7.0	7.6
1.00	7.8	5.00	8.9	9.2
1.00	11.8	5.00	12.5	13.9
1.00	5.00	0.0	0.3	-
1.00	5.00	1.00	1.4	1.1
1.00	5.00	3.00	3.4	3.5
1.00	5.00	5.00	5.3	5.9
1.00	5.00	7.50	7.0	8.8
1.00	5.00	10.0	8.0	11.0

Initial rates were calculated using K_{eq} and k as $60.4 \pm 6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $627.0 \pm 15 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively

Effect of sulphate : Since Mn^{III} can form sulphate complexes, runs were followed with varying sulphate concentrations keeping all other conditions constant in perchlorate-perchloric acid media. Added sulphate did not lead to any recognisable effect on the reaction.

The bromide catalysed oxidation of As^{III} by Mn^{III} in a strong sulphuric acid follows on approximate rate law shown in equation (1), the orders in As^{III} and bromide concentrations being fractional. Acid and initial presence of products did not affect the reaction in the concentration ranges studied. The possibility that the orders in two extreme cases [oxidant] >> [reductant] and [reductant] >> [oxidant] would be different as in the case of iodide catalysed Ce^{IV} oxidation⁵ of As^{III} was also ruled out as it was found in the two extreme cases also that the order remained approximately the same with respect

to oxidant and reductant concentrations. The rate data are comparable with the reaction going through a substrate-halide complex followed by intervention of arsenic(IV) as shown in Scheme 1.

$$\frac{-d}{dt} [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}] = k[\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}] [\text{As}^{\text{III}}]^{0.57} [\text{Br}^-]^{0.7} \quad (1)$$

Although Mn^{III} can form MnBr₂⁺ similar to MnCl₂⁺, the fact that its equilibrium constant is small⁶ and that the measured order in Mn^{III} is approximately unity, shows that MnBr₂⁺ which is present under the present experimental conditions to the extent of about 1% may not be involved and aquated Mn^{III} might be the active species. Furthermore, experiments with varying sulphate concentrations keeping all other concentrations constant in perchlorate media also showed that sulphate is without influence on the reaction. Hence, sulphate complexes are also not involved. It is well understood that not only species such as AsBr₃, AsCl₃ have high stability⁷ but also equilibrium constants of different SbCl_x^{+3-x} complexes are known⁸ to have substantial values, x indicating one to six chlorides. In view of similarity of As^{III} and Sb^{III} halide complexes, the known equilibrium constants of SbCl_x^{+3-x} may be used to make

Scheme 1

an approximate estimate of the concentrations of different As^{III}-bromide complexes. Such concentrations calculated by an approximate method⁹ accounting for the competing equilibria, are shown in Table 2 along with the corresponding experimentally determined rates in the case of different bromide concentrations used.

It was found that a ready parallelism between concentration and rates occurs only in the case of the species involving only one halide, AsBr₂⁺ and not in others – reinforcing the possibility of the latter participation in the mechanism (as in Scheme

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CATALYST, [Br⁻] IN BROMIDE CATALYSED OXIDATION OF As^{III} BY Mn^{III} IN ACID MEDIUMTemp = 25°, [As^{III}] = 1.0 × 10⁻², [Mn^{III}] = 5.0 × 10⁻³, [H₂SO₄] = 5.0, *l* = 5.60 mol dm⁻³

[Br ⁻] × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³	[As ^{III}] × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	[AsBr ²⁺] × 10 ⁶ mol dm ⁻³	[AsBr ₂ ⁺] × 10 ⁹ mol dm ⁻³	[AsBr ₃] × 10 ¹² mol dm ⁻³	[AsBr ₄] × 10 ¹⁶ mol dm ⁻³	Rate × 10 ⁵ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹	
						Exptl.	Calcd.*
0.0	—	—	—	—	—	0.3	—
1.0	9.998	1.799	0.3019	0.0149	0.0052	1.4	1.1
3.0	9.995	5.397	2.788	0.4047	0.4290	3.4	3.5
5.0	9.997	8.997	7.743	1.868	3.309	5.3	5.9
7.5	9.986	13.25	17.40	6.319	16.73	7.0	8.8
10.0	9.982	17.96	30.94	14.97	52.90	8.0	11.0

* Rates were calculated using K_{eq} and k as $60.4 \pm 6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $627.0 \pm 15 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively (Eq. 4); error $\pm 5\%$.

1). In terms of Scheme (1), a rate law (5) may be derived as follows. The concentration of As^{III}-bromide complex (AsBr²⁺) is given by equation (2),

$$[\text{AsBr}^{2+}] = K_{eq}[\text{As}^{\text{III}}][\text{Br}^-] \quad (2)$$

The rate of disappearance of [Mn^{III}] with time is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k[\text{AsBr}^{2+}][\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}] \\ &= k K_{eq}[\text{As}^{\text{III}}][\text{Br}^-][\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{As}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} &= [\text{As}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{f}} + K_{eq}[\text{As}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{f}}[\text{Br}^-] \\ &= [\text{As}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{f}}[1 + K_{eq}[\text{Br}^-]] \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{T}} &= [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{f}} + K_{eq}[\text{Br}^-]_{\text{f}}[\text{As}^{\text{III}}] \\ &= [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{f}}[1 + K_{eq}[\text{As}^{\text{III}}]] \end{aligned}$$

equation (3) becomes equation (4),

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k K_{eq} [\text{As}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{Br}^-]_{\text{T}} [\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}]}{1 + K_{eq} [\text{As}^{\text{III}}] + K_{eq} [\text{Br}^-] + K_{eq}^2 [\text{As}^{\text{III}}] [\text{Br}^-]} \quad (4)$$

The rate law (4) accounts for the fractional orders of [As^{III}]_T as well as [Br⁻]_T and may be verified in the form of equation (5) at constant [Br⁻] by plotting left-hand-side against [As^{III}].

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{[\text{As}^{\text{III}}][\text{Mn}^{\text{III}}][\text{Br}^-]}{\text{Rate}} \\ &= \left\{ \frac{1}{k} + \frac{K_{eq}[\text{Br}^-]}{k} \right\} [\text{As}^{\text{III}}] + \frac{1}{kK_{eq}} + \frac{[\text{Br}^-]}{k} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The linearity of such a plot verifies Scheme 1. Further confirmation of Scheme 1 is had by evaluat-

ing K_{eq} and k from graph and utilising the latter constants to calculate rates for different situations. K_{eq} and k derived from graphs were $60.4 \pm 6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $627.0 \pm 15 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. Using equation (4), calculated rates were found to compare reasonably with the corresponding experimental rates (Table 1).

The present reaction has been studied in presence of chloride ions. It is found that the catalytic activity of bromide is more than that of chloride, indicating the ease of electron transfer or effectiveness of the bridge decreases in the order $\text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$ which is in agreement with the work of Ogard and Taube¹⁰. The difference in the rates of halogen transfer is expected, for the most polarisable ligand is likely to transfer most easily¹¹. Activation parameters were not calculated as the rates measured corresponded to a multistep mechanism.

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used. A stock solution of sodium bromide (B.D.H.) was prepared in distilled water. A stock solution of arsenic(III) was made by dissolving arsenic(III) oxide (AnalaR) in 1.0 mol dm⁻³ NaOH and standardised with potassium bromate¹². The base in the arsenic(III) solution was neutralised by adding the requisite amount of the acid in the preparation of the reaction mixture. Arsenic(V) was prepared by dissolving potassium orthoarsenate (Riedel) in water. The manganese(III) solution in almost all experiments was prepared¹³ freshly as it was found to degrade by approximately 3% in 24 h.

Kinetic run : Kinetic runs were initiated by mixing

the previously thermostated solutions of Mn^{III} and As^{III} which also contained bromide, equivalent amount of sulphuric acid and the required amount of sodium sulphate. The reactions were followed by measuring the absorbance of Mn^{III} in the reaction mixture at different time intervals at 500 nm in a 1 cm cell using a Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer. Beer's law of Mn^{III} solution at different acid concentrations was tested earlier ($\epsilon = 114 \pm 2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Most of the kinetic runs were studied at $5.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and 5.6 mol dm^{-3} ionic strength, obtained from *in situ* calculated free H^+ , HSO_4^- and SO_4^{2-} and the sulphate added to the solution. The $[H^+]$ values were calculated from added H_2SO_4 concentration and $[SO_4^{2-}]$ from sulphate equilibrium¹⁴ constant. Initial rates were obtained from plots of $[Mn^{III}]$ vs time. Rates of reaction were reproducible to within $\pm 4\%$. Temperature were maintained within $\pm 0.10^\circ$. Ionic strength was kept constant using sulphate. Most of the reactions were followed to 80% or above.

Stoichiometry : Different reaction mixtures containing various sets of concentrations of reactants with a constant amount of catalyst, bromide ($5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), sulphuric acid (5 mol dm^{-3}) and ionic strength (5.60 mol dm^{-3}) were allowed to react over 24 h at room temperature and then analysed for Mn^{III} , As^{III} and As^V . Mn^{III} was found by measuring its absorbance of 500 nm. As^{III} was estimated by titrating with bromate¹² using methyl orange as indicator and the product As^V was found iodometrically¹² by titrating with thiosulphate. The results were in agreement with the stoichiometry of one mole of As^{III} to two moles of Mn^{III} reacted as in equation (6),

The catalyst (bromide) concentration was found by measuring the amount of precipitate formed with silver nitrate before and after the reaction using a Systronics nepheloturbidimeter 131. The amount of precipitate found before and after the reaction was the same, the agreement was total with an error of less than 1.0%.

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